

THE COURSE OF COMMUNITY-ACQUIRED PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN FROM 3-7 YEARS OLD, DEPENDING ON VACCINE PROPHYLAXIS

¹Kuryazova Sh. M., ²Khudainazarova S. R., ³Ilkhomova H.A., ⁴Razhabova N.

^{1,2,3,4}Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12355356>

Annotation. *To study the clinical course of community-acquired pneumonia depending on specific prophylaxis against pneumococcal infection. We examined 120 children aged 3-7 years with a diagnosis of community-acquired pneumonia (CAP), who were undergoing inpatient treatment at the TashPMI clinic in the pulmonology department. As a result of the study, it was determined that in the groups of children who received a full course of vaccination against pneumococcal infection and in children with a violation of the immunization regimen, the course of CAP differed in the nature of the onset of the disease, the severity of respiratory failure, fever, and shortness of breath.*

Keyword: *children, pneumonia, vaccine prevention, pneumococcus.*

Relevance. Pneumonia is a major problem for pulmonologists, pediatricians, and doctors of family clinics, due to its relatively high incidence and prevalence in various age groups of children. Streptococcus pneumoniae is the main causative agent of pneumonia, more than 95% of pneumococcal pneumonias are community-acquired [3, 4]. Among children and adults, pneumococcal infection is a common cause of morbidity and mortality in many countries of the world. According to WHO, about 1 million children die from various forms of pneumococcal infection every year. Currently, mortality from diseases caused by pneumococcal infection can be prevented by vaccination [6.5]. Immunization with a polyvalent pneumococcal vaccine is one of the main modern directions of the fight to reduce morbidity and mortality in VP [5,6].

The high effectiveness of vaccination against pneumococcal infection in children and adults, demonstrated in various countries of the world, allows us to consider immunization as one of the main components in a strategy to reduce the incidence of pneumonia. When using the pneumococcal conjugate vaccine Preventar-13, the total incidence of children decreased 2.3 times, the duration of the disease decreased by 14.6%, the number of courses of antibacterial therapy decreased by 21.3%, the number of hospitalizations - by 38.4%, the number of days of disability of their parents - by 11.1%, which indicates high medical and social economic efficiency vaccinations.

A favorable prognosis for pneumonia is determined by timely vaccination, early diagnosis and an adequate choice of starting antibacterial therapy, while timely diagnosis is based on the results of a detailed and consistent analysis of clinical, anamnestic and radiological data. To date, two vaccines have been registered and approved for use in Uzbekistan for the prevention of pneumococcal infection, fundamentally different in composition and tactics of use – polysaccharide 23-valent ("Pneumo-23") for children over 2 years of age and adults and conjugated 10-valent ("Preventar") [5,6,7].

In this regard, a study analyzing the clinical and anatomical and morphological characteristics of pneumonia at the present time, which is important for its timely diagnosis, as well as the dependence of the occurrence of the disease on the availability of vaccination carried out in a particular region, is of particular relevance and scientific significance.

Aim. To determine the clinical course of community-acquired pneumonia depending on vaccine prophylaxis in preschool children.

Material and methods. 120 children aged 3-7 years with a diagnosis of community-acquired pneumonia (VP) who were on inpatient treatment at the TashPMI clinic in the pulmonology department were examined. The children were divided into 2 groups: 1 group of patients – 78 (65%) who did not receive the specific 13-valent vaccine Preventar, according to the calendar of preventive vaccinations against pneumococcal infection; 2 group - 42 (35%) patients who received the calendar of preventive vaccinations, 13-valent vaccine Preventar. All children underwent clinical and anamnestic (complaints, anamnesis of the disease and objective data) examination methods, instrumental (chest X-ray, pulse oximetry, ECG, conventional laboratory tests. The severity of pneumonia in children during hospitalization was determined on the recommendation of WHO Order No. 225 on "Inpatient care for children", which corresponded to the indicator of the need for hospitalization and treatment [2]. Statistical processing of the obtained results was carried out using MS Excel and Statistica 6.0 programs. The reliability of the difference in relative values was determined by the accuracy index (p) depending on the Student's confidence coefficient (t), the differences were considered significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results and discussions. From the analysis of medical histories and a survey of parents, 90% of the cases in the anamnesis of children in group 1 were ill from 4 or more times a year with acute respiratory infections (ARI) and were admitted to the hospital in a serious condition due to severe endogenous intoxication, respiratory insufficiency (DN), hemodynamic and microcirculation disorders. In group 1, children suffered from combined ENT pathologies - 85.7% of cases (grade 1-2 adenoiditis, rhinopharyngitis, sinusitis, chronic tonsillitis). Patients in group 2, 36% of cases had acute respiratory infections 1-3 times a year, and 34.7% had various ENT pathologies ($p \leq 0.001$). It should be noted that in the studied groups, children of group 1 differed in the frequent development of pneumonia. In the anamnesis, recurrent pneumonia was registered 2 or more times a year in patients of group 1 (68.3%) than in group 2 patients - 5.6%, which had significant statistical significance ($p < 0.001$). Comorbid diseases in children of group 1 were manifested by atopic dermatitis (44.8%), irritable bowel syndrome (38.9%), residual rickets (23.6%), and in children of 2-group (Fig.1).

Fig.1. Clinical symptoms in children with out-of-hospital pneumonia

During the examination of patients, it was revealed that a severe course of community-acquired pneumonia with febrile hyperthermia was observed, as shown in the figure (Fig.1), in children of

group 1 n= 42 (53.9%), and with subfebrile temperature with a moderate degree of VP - n = 36 (46.1%), and in In the second group, febrile temperature was noted at - n= 4 (9.5%) ($p \leq 0.001$), and subfebrile temperature was noted at n= 38 (90.4%) ($p \leq 0.001$). Febrile hyperthermia was observed in 60.6% of vaccinated children with severe VP. Subfebrile body temperature was observed in 100% of vaccinated children with mild pneumonia. This circumstance indicates a more favorable picture of respiratory syndrome in vaccinated older children. Cough of a productive nature was observed in 100% of children in both groups. The analysis of the severity of dyspnea as the main objective indicator of respiratory failure was clearly manifested in children with severe pneumonia, dyspnea was mixed, n= 70 (89.4%) occurred, in group 2 it was present in only n= 12 (28.5%). The average duration of shortness of breath was 7.5 ± 1.5 days in children of group 1, and 4.0 ± 1.0 days in group 2. Intoxication syndrome, manifested by asthenization phenomena, decreased appetite, headache and muscle pain, was detected in group 1 of children -90.4% and in group 2 15.6%. During the examination, increased sweating was observed in children of group 1 more often than in group 2 – in (58.3%) and (23.6%), respectively. Acrocyanosis cyanosis and marbling of the skin were also observed more often in children of group 1 in the ratio of -36.6% and 11.6% , in contrast to group 2 – in 13.3% and 5.5% ($p < 0.05$). An increase in peripheral lymph nodes was found in most children of group 1 – 16.0%, and in group 2 - 3.3% ($p \leq 0.001$). In children with severe acute pneumonia, 54.5% of respiratory and circulatory disorders were detected, 3 children had a minimal degree of heart failure.

Fig.2.Comorbid pathologies in children with out-of-hospital pneumonia

Retarded physical development (PEU-1CO) the risk of underweight was observed in children of group 1 -35.6 versus 10.3%, and the risk of overweight PEU +2CO in the pear was 23.5% versus 6.7% It is also worth noting deficiency conditions According to the analysis of insufficiency of vitamin B12, folic acid, and the microelement calcium, more were detected in children of group 1 - 34.5 versus 3.4%%, which was statistically significant on average ($p < 0.001$). Physical data from the lungs in children of both groups were determined by the volume of the lesion and the localization of pneumonic changes. During auscultation in children of groups 1 and 2, moist rales and weakened breathing were heard in the affected areas. An important criterion for the severity of the children's condition was symptoms of DN. In children of group 2, 75.0% were diagnosed with DN of the 1st degree, while y of group 1 were not diagnosed. II degree DN was observed in children of group 1 in 68.9% and in group 2 25%, and III degree of DN occurred only in children of group 1 in 31.1% of children. All children with grade III DN were transferred to the intensive care unit. From the cardiovascular system, in group 1 with pneumonia, almost every third

(30.0% of children) had muffled heart sounds and every fourth (25.0% of children) had a systolic murmur at the apex, and in group 2, muffled heart sounds were heard 13.3% of children and systolic murmur at the apex in 5% of children. Analysis of the results of an X-ray examination (OGC) showed that children of group 1 were diagnosed with segmental 55.8% and lobar 44.2% pneumonia; in children of group 2, focal pneumonia was more common - 63.8%, segmental - 36.2%.

Laboratory criteria characteristic of community-acquired pneumonia were classic. Leukocytosis with a shift to the left was noted in 100% of patients ($p < 0.05$); increase in erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) - 89.5% and in the second group 53.8% ($p > 0.05$). Lymphopenia was detected in 39 children of the 2nd group (58.2%), and lymphocytosis in vaccinated children of the 1st group - 35 (53.8%). It should be noted that in children with severe pneumonia there were significant differences in the rates of leukocytosis and ESR, namely their high level - over 12×10^9 and over 35 mm/h, respectively.

The frequency of occurrence of concomitant diseases in children of group 1 was manifested: anemia grade 1-2 (45.6%), atopic dermatitis (44.8%), irritable bowel syndrome (38.9%), biliary dyskinesia (13.6%), atopic dermatitis -5.7%, shown in Fig.2.

Conclusions. As a result of the study, it was determined that in the groups of children who received a full course of vaccination against pneumococcal infection and in children with a violation of the immunization regimen, the course of CAP differed in the nature of the onset of the disease, the severity of respiratory failure, fever, and shortness of breath. Dyspnea as the main objective indicator of DN was clearly manifested in children with severe disease, Children in group 1 did not receive immunization against pneumococcal infection in 89.4% of cases, and in group 2 - 28.5%, and higher levels of ESR and leukocytes were also noted. Thus, vaccination of children against pneumococcal infection should be mandatory, which will reduce severe pneumonia.

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